

**PERCEPTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS
ON THEIR SATISFACTION OF LEVELS 1 – 3 OF MASLOW’S
HIERARCHY OF NEEDS IN KOGI EAST SENATORIAL
DISTRICT OF KOGI STATE, NIGERIA**

Helen Agashi¹,

Agashi Pius Petinga²

Ezeike Anthonia Ekwutosi²

¹College of Arabic and Islamic Studies,
Ankpa, Nigeria

²Kogi State College of Education, Ankpa,
Nigeria

Abstract:

The study was on the perception of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of Levels 1 – 3 of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs in Kogi East Senatorial District of Kogi State, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 302 secondary school teachers from three randomly selected council areas in the district. A survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The research instrument was “Teachers Perception of Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs Questionnaire” (TPMHNQ). TPMHNQ was constructed by the researchers and validated by three experts in the Department of Curriculum & Teaching, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria. The reliability of the instrument was calculated using Cronbach Alpha and the internal consistency was found to be 0.73. The instrument was administered on the sample with the aid of two research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using Mean to answer the research questions and Chi-Square to test the hypotheses. Among other findings were; (i) level 1 and 2 of Maslow’s hierarchy are not completely satisfied, (ii) level 3 of Maslow’s hierarchy is not satisfied at all, (iii) the satisfaction of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs is depended on teachers qualification ($p < 0.05$), (iv) satisfaction of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs is dependent on gender ($p < 0.05$). Based on the findings, some recommendations were put forward among which are, (i) effort should be made by government in the areas of prompt payment of teachers’ salaries and allowances, (ii) government should provide good working conditions, (iii) teachers should be sponsored by government to workshops / conferences on regular basis to up-date their knowledge.

Keywords: secondary school teachers, Maslow’s hierarchy of needs, Kogi East Senatorial District, Nigeria

1. Introduction

Human resources are the most precious asset of any institution. The desire of any human organization or institution irrespective of kind is the attainment of the goals and objectives. The attainment of the goal to a large extent depends on the human resources that constitute the cornerstone of any institution. The extent to which the goals are achieved is directly linked to the ability to manage the staff which is a product of motivation.

Motivation is derived from the Latin word “moucre” which means to “move” (Nwachukwu, 2006). Schulge and Steyn (2003) affirmed that in order to understand people’s behaviour at work, supervisor must be aware of the concept of need or motives which will help move the employee to act. Motivation is a need-satisfying process which means that when a person’s needs are satisfied by certain factors, the person may exert more effort towards attaining the stipulated goals.

Motivation is the management process of influencing behaviour based on the knowledge of what makes people do things (Luther, 2005). Motivation is defined also as what pushes someone to do things in order to achieve something (Salma & Sajid, 2012). Motivation is such a factor that exerts a driving force on someone’s action and work. A highly motivated team of employees helps in attaining the target of an organization or institution.

The prime place of motivation in an organization is aptly captured by Khan Ford, an American industrialist when he said that take my business, burn up my building, but give me people and I will build the business right back again, (Khan, 2011). Rosenfelt and Wilson (2003) defined motivation as the process that stimulates the teachers to put their full effort in order to achieve a desired task. Motivation is the process that energizes, directs, arouses and sustains the behaviour and performance of the employee. Ikenyiri (2007) states that motivation is an internal arousal, which directs and maintains achieving, set goals. These definitions have not only stated the meaning of motivation, but also made inputs on the role of motivation to the worker. A motivated worker is easy to spot by his or her agility, education, enthusiasm, focus, zeal and general performance and contribution to the organizational or institutional objectives and goals (Ifinedo, 2003).

The relationship among satisfaction of needs, motivation and job satisfaction has increasingly attracted the attention of social scientists and researchers as this is capable of making or marring the corporate existence and attainment of stated goals of any institution.

Over the years social scientists have attempted to propound theories of motivation. They believed there are several factors that motivate workers to perform their work satisfactorily. One of such social scientists is Abraham Maslow (1954) who propounded the need based theory of motivation. The theory provided a hierarchy of factors in form of needs whose satisfaction motivates an employee. These needs are Physiological (basic needs) (Level 1), Safety and security (Level 2), Affection (love and belonging) (Level 3), Self Esteem (Level 4) and Self Actualization (Level 5). Maslow

(1954) argued that individuals have a hierarchy of needs which are in the following order: physiological needs which involve the needs to satisfy hunger, thirst, clothing, housing. Second; safety needs, needs to feel safe, secure and stable. Third, social needs, needs to love and be loved, to belong and be accepted. Fourth, esteem needs, needs for self-esteem, achievement and respect from others. Fifth, self-actualization needs. Needs to live up to one's fullest and unique potential (Myers, 2013).

The satisfaction of a need at a lower level leads to the activation of the need at the next level. According to McClelland and Burnham (2004) needs are most commonly referred to as a person's conscious want, desires or motives. Needs, satisfaction and motivation to work are very essential in the lives of teachers because they form the fundamental reasons for working in life. While almost every teacher works in order to satisfy his/her needs in life, he or she constantly agitates for needs satisfaction. An alternative view defines needs in term of nutrients that are essential for survival, growth and integrity of individual (Ryan, Sheldon, Kasser & Deci, 1996).

There are needs that take priority over other needs. Maslow argues that the physiological needs when satisfied motivate or is a step towards the achievement of other needs. He believes that people who are often distracted from seeking self-actualization needs are capable of their inability to meet their basic needs (Bernstein, Clarke-Stewart, Peanner, Ray & Wickens, 2000). Psychological needs are needs that require immediate attention. They consist in the basic biological needs which include the needs for food, water, air, shelter and clothing. When any of these needs goes unsatisfied, the individual becomes preoccupied and lacks concentration and coordination (Igbo, 2013). When the physiological needs are not satisfied, no other needs will serve as basis for motivation. But once they are satisfied, then newer needs emerge. In the school system, the salary one earns enables one to satisfy one's needs but if unfulfilled, then result to dissatisfaction which affects productivity and quality performance in the work place. If an individual's needs are not met at the basement level, definitely they cannot scale the hierarchy and he fail to attain their true potential. For Ramalingam (2006), physiological motives which involves motive stemming from bodily need is very important to lives of individuals. Whenever physiological needs are captured in individual's lives then equilibration is set for further action.

Safety needs emerge once the physiological needs have been achieved. This includes the need for security, safety, protection against danger and accidents, threats against one's job satisfaction, in the physical and internal events of day to day life. In the school, teachers want to have the feeling that their jobs are secured and accommodation also secured. When such is lacking, it threatens their performance and work commitment. Peretomode (2003) observed that these needs are often met in the educational institutions by granting teachers such programme like fringe benefits, promotion, retirement or pension schemes, insurance benefits, welfare benefits, free medical and health service, job security and safe working conditions.

Social needs include the need for love, affection, companionship, acceptance and friendship, sense of belonging in one's relationship with others. Maslow states that people seek to overcome feelings of loneliness and alienation. This involves both giving

and receiving love and affection. In the school, social needs of teachers are usually satisfied if informal group and teacher's participation in decision making is encouraged, membership in groups also encouraged and proper delegation of duty. Once found lacking or not satisfied, affects their psychology / mental health resulting to absenteeism, poor performance, low job satisfaction and emotional breakdown. Ofojebe and Ezugoh (2010) emphasized on need to maintain a democratic atmosphere in schools since teachers are by and large sensitive human being and professionals who in most cases, can do their job satisfactorily without too much bossing. What teachers actually want is to provide a working climate that will help them do their job better and an opportunity for professional advancement and the satisfaction of their needs within the school/organization.

The motivation of teachers in Nigeria has received little attention despite the fact that research has demonstrated just how important the teachers' influence is on students' motivation. Research in general has tended to focus more on the motivation of learner than on the teacher's motivation despite the fact that the teacher's level of enthusiasm and commitment is one of the most important factors that affect the learners' motivation. For instance, secondary school teachers in Nigeria have complained of government inability to attend to their needs. Their salaries are not paid as at when due, their promotion is delayed and when implemented the arrears are not paid. There may be no doubt that this affects the socio-economic status of teachers which is a function of the satisfaction of human needs in line with Maslow's theory.

2. Statement of the Problem

The relationship among need satisfaction, motivation and job satisfaction has attracted the attention of social scientists and researchers (eg Herzberg, 1954; Ifedili & Ifedili, 2012) as this has the potential to make or mar the realization of the goals of any institution. One of such social scientist is Abraham Maslow (1970) who linked motivation to the satisfaction of human needs. These needs are inform of a 5 level hierarchy. Maslow (1970) argued that individuals have 5 basic human needs which are arranged according to levels of importance or hierarchy starting with the lowest (most basic needs). These are: physiological needs (hunger, thirst, clothing and housing), safety needs (need to love and be loved), self-esteem needs (achievement, respect for others) and self-actualization needs (needs to live up to one's fullness and unique potentials).

Maslow postulated that the satisfaction of the lower level of needs serve as a motivation to work for the satisfaction of the next level. The needs satisfaction of teachers derives from the condition under which they work which includes regularity of salaries, allowances, leave bonuses, staff development and other work incentives. Over the years, unfortunately, secondary school teachers in Nigeria have complained of government inability to satisfy their needs. Their salaries are not paid as at when due, their promotion is delayed and when implemented, the arrears are not paid. However, there is no known documented evidence to the knowledge of the researchers on how

the teachers perceive satisfaction of human needs in line with Maslow's theory in Kogi East Senatorial District. This has created the need for this study. The problem of the study therefore, is to find out the perception of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of Levels 1 – 3 of Maslow's hierarchy of needs in Kogi East Senatorial District of Kogi State, Nigeria.

3. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study is to determine the perception of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of levels 1 – 3 of Maslow's hierarchy of needs in Kogi East Senatorial District of Kogi State. Specifically, the study aims to find:

- 1) The mean response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the physiological needs.
- 2) The mean response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the safety needs.
- 3) The mean response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the social needs.

3.1 Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- 1) What is the mean response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the physiological needs of Maslow needs hierarchy?
- 2) What is the mean response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the safety needs of Maslow needs hierarchy?
- 3) What is the mean response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the social needs of Maslow needs hierarchy?

3.2 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- 1) The response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of levels 1 – 3 of Maslow needs hierarchy is not significantly dependent on their qualification.
- 2) The response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of levels 1 – 3 of Maslow needs hierarchy is not significantly dependent on their gender.
- 3) The response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of level 1 – 3 of Maslow needs hierarchy is not significantly dependent on their location.

3.3 Significance of the Study

The study on the perception of secondary school teachers on the satisfaction of Level 1 – 3 of Maslow hierarchy of needs may be of immense benefit to teachers, government, students and other stakeholders in education.

For the teachers, the study may afford them a platform to air their view on how they feel or think about their socio-economic status with a view to attracting the needed attention from the educational authorities with the hope of addressing them. This can be achieved through seminars, workshops and conferences.

For government, the study may serve as a barometer to gauge its obligation to the teachers and make the necessary adjustments towards remediation in the area of prompt payment of salaries, allowances and other welfare packages. This can be achieved through the advocacy of teachers association such as Nigeria Union of Teachers (NUT).

For the students, the benefits derivable from the teachers and government could translate into job satisfaction of the teachers and by extension improved performance on the part of both the teachers and students. This is obvious because when teacher's needs are satisfied, they can perform at optimum level, therefore facilitating teaching and learning for the benefit of the learners.

Finally, all other stakeholders in education, parents, administrators etc. may benefit if teachers needs are identified and addressed as this will lead to improvement in teaching and learning and performance of students which is the ultimate aim of the stakeholders in education.

3.4 Research Design

The design of this study is a survey research design. It is a survey design because it involves the views of a group of people studied by collecting and analyzing data from a few people considered to be a representative sample of the entire population (Emaikwu, 2013). The design is appropriate for the study because it involves the views or belief (perception) of people (teachers) on existing conditions (Maslow's hierarchy of needs).

3.5 Area of Study

The study is carried out in Kogi East Senatorial District of Kogi State. This senatorial district is made of nine local council areas namely: Ankpa, Bassa, Dekina, Omalla, Idah, Olamaboro, Ofu, Igalamela Odolu and Ibaji. The area is dominated by the Igala speaking ethnic group in Kogi State. It is bounded to the south with Enugu State, to the west with Anambra State, to the east with Benue State and to the north with River Benue/Niger.

The post primary institutions in the area are state owned and private secondary schools. The state owned secondary schools are in the majority. The study focused only on state owned secondary schools because of uniformity of working conditions in the schools. The teachers in government owned schools are all professionals since they are certified by the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria, (TRCN). Their qualifications range from NCE to PhD in various disciplines. The choice of Kogi East Senatorial District for the study is because it has the highest number of secondary school teachers compared to other two senatorial districts, (Teaching Service Commission, TSC, 2015).

3.6 Population

The population of the study comprises all the secondary school teachers in Kogi East Senatorial District, totaling 1,354, (TSC, 2015).

3.7 Sample and Sampling

The sample for the study is 302 secondary school teachers from 3 randomly selected council areas in the district. The sample was obtained as follows: 3 out of the 9 local government areas in Kogi East Senatorial District were selected through simple random sampling technique (balloting). The 3 local government councils selected were: Omalla, Olamoboro and Igalamela-Odolu. All the secondary school teachers in the 3 local government totaling 302 (TSC, 2015) were used as purposive sample since it is possible for the researchers to access all of them.

3.8 Instrument

The instrument for the study was “Teachers Perception of Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs Questionnaire” (TPMHNQ) constructed by the researchers on a 4 point Likert scale.

3.9 Validation of the Instrument(s)

TPMHNQ was validated by three lecturers in Benue State University, Makurdi and an experienced social science educator in Kogi State College of Education, Ankpa. The validation indicated that some statements in the items were not personalized. These corrections were effected. All the items were retained.

3.10 Reliability

The reliability of the instrument was calculated using Cronbach alpha and the internal consistency was found to be 0.73.

3.11 Method of Data Collection

The data for the study were the responses of the teachers to the items of the instrument, which was administered on the sample for the study through the aid two research assistants. All the 302 respondents returned the instrument.

3.12 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and Chi-square for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 percent level of significance.

4. Results

The analysis is according to the research questions. For the research questions, a mean value of 2.5 and above indicates agreement to the items, otherwise, it indicates disagreement.

Research Question 1: What is the mean response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the physiological needs of Maslow needs hierarchy?

Table 1: Mean rating of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of physiological needs

Item	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Remark
1. Even though my monthly pay may not be enough for my needs, I am able to cope.	302	3.29	0.76	A
2. Providing for daily food need of my family does not pose a problem to me.	302	2.50	0.91	A
3. Payment of house rent does not pose big challenge to me.	302	2.45	0.97	D
4. Having my own house is not a possibility	302	2.03	1.09	D
5. Clothing for my household is affordable.	302	3.02	0.87	A
6. I am comfortable with the working conditions as a teacher.	302	2.64	0.95	A
7. I have no problem accessing portable water in my area.	302	2.63	1.03	A
8. As a teacher, I do lose sleep thinking of my condition of service.	302	2.66	0.97	A
Cluster Mean		2.65		
A = Agree, D = Disagree				

Table 1 above reveals that out of the eight items under physiological needs, majority of the teachers agreed with 6 of the items (items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8) and disagreed with the remaining two items (items 3 and 4). Majority of teachers are not comfortable with their condition of service and payment of house rent. A cluster mean of 2.65 which is above the cut off mean of 2.50 is an indication of teachers' perception that their physiological needs are satisfied.

Research Question 2: What is the response of secondary school teachers in Kogi east on their perception of satisfaction of the safety needs of Maslow hierarchy.

Table 2: Mean rating of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of safety needs

Item	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Remark
1. My job is not threatened by any government policies.	302	2.74	1.01	A
2. My job is threatened by my boss.	302	2.12	0.91	D
3. Pursuit of further studies is not a threat to my job.	302	2.96	0.95	A
4. There is a fair treatment to all staff in my establishment.	302	2.42	0.88	D
5. Health care service is provided for all staff by my establishment.	302	2.10	1.02	D
6. I have fear for safety in the classroom and school environment.	302	2.41	0.95	D
7. There is no fear over protection against dismissal or undue transfer by my employer.	302	2.06	1.12	D
Cluster Mean		2.48		
A = Agree, D = Disagree				

Table 2 shows that out of 7 items on the satisfaction of safety needs of secondary school teachers, some of the teachers agree with only 2 of the items (items 9, 11), while some are in disagreement with 5 of the items (items 10, 12, 13, 14, 15) with the cluster mean of 2.48 which is less than the bench mark of 2.50, majority of the teachers are in disagreement with the items on safety needs of Maslow's hierarchy. The implication is that safety needs of the teachers are largely not satisfied.

Research Question 3: What is the mean response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of their social needs of Maslow's need of hierarchy?

Table 3: Mean rating of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of social needs

Item	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Remark
1. I am not loved by my students and their parent.	302	1.80	0.99	D
2. I am respected by members of my work community.	302	3.33	0.74	A
3. My relationship with my colleagues is cordial.	302	3.35	0.95	A
4. I am appreciated by the school authority.	302	2.11	0.85	D
5. My relationship with my school authority is cordial.	302	1.90	0.94	D
6. I am not allowed to participate actively to the formation of my school rules.	302	3.14	0.74	A
Cluster Mean		2.61		
A = Agree, D = Disagree				

Table 3 shows that some of the teachers agree to 3 of the 6 items (items 17, 18, 21) and some disagreed with the other 3 items (item 16, 19, 20). However, with a cluster mean of 2.61, it can be inferred that most of the teachers are in agreement that their social needs of Maslow hierarchy are satisfied.

Hypotheses 1: The response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the level of Maslow’s needs hierarchy is not significantly dependent on their qualification.

Table 4: Ho1: chi-square test on teacher’s satisfaction of Levels 1 – 3 of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs on bases of qualification

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual	Chi square Value	Df	Asymp. sig	Remark
Strongly Disagree	25	75.5	-50.5	129.656	6	0.000	S
Disagree	35	75.5	-40.5				
Agree	148	75.5	72.5				
Strongly Agree	94	75.5	18.5				
Total	302						

S = significant.

Table 4 shows chi-square value of 129.66 with $p=0.00$. Since $p<0.05$, it means that the response of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of Maslow’s need hierarchy is significantly dependent on their qualification. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the responses of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of Maslow’s needs hierarchy on the basis of qualification are significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypotheses 2: The response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the level of Maslow needs hierarchy is not significantly dependent on their gender.

Table 5: Ho2: Chi-square test on teachers’ satisfaction of Levels 1 – 3 of Maslow’s hierarchy needs on basis of gender

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual	Chi Square Value	Df	Asymp. Sig	Remark
Strongly Disagree	47	75.5	-28.5	46.37	3	0.000	S
Disagree	68	75.5	-7.5				
Agree	125	75.5	49.5				
Strongly Agree	62	75.5	-13.5				
Total	302						

Table 5 shows chi-square value of 48.37 with $p = 0.00$. Since $p<0.05$, it means that the responses of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of Maslow’s needs hierarchy are significantly dependent on gender. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypotheses 3: The response of secondary school teachers in Kogi East on their perception of satisfaction of the level of Maslow’s needs hierarchy is not significantly dependent on their location.

Table 6: H03: Chi-square test on teacher’s satisfaction of Levels 1 – 3 of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs on the basis of location

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual	Chi Square Value	Df	Asymp. Sig	Remark
Strongly Disagree	38	75.5	-37.5	89.709	3	0.000	S
Agree	141	75.5	65.5				
Disagree	80	75.5	4.5				
Strongly Agree	43	75.5	-32.5				
Total	302						

Table 6 shows chi-square value of 89.71 with $p = 0.00$. Since $p < 0.05$, it means that the response of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of Maslow’s needs hierarchy is significantly dependent on their location. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

5. Discussion of Result

From Table 1, out of the 8 items surveyed under physiological need of the teachers, the only two items that some of the teachers perceived as posing a challenge are: their working condition or condition of service and payment of house rent.

The working condition which poses a challenge to some of the teachers may not be unconnected with irregular payment of salaries and allowances in form of annual leave bonus. The challenge of payment of house rent may not be unconnected with the irregular payment of salary and allowances. With mean response of 3.29 on their satisfaction of monthly pay, it can be inferred that the majority of the teachers are not complaining about their monthly take home. In line with this, there is the agreement that the provision for food is not a challenge to the teachers. That majority of the teachers disagreed that having their own house is not a possibility, that is, they are hopeful of owning their own houses, is an indication that with regular payment of salaries and allowances, their savings from monthly emolument can afford a house.

Access to portable water does not pose a challenge to majority of the teachers as shown from the mean response of 2.63. From the foregoing, majority of the teachers seem to have expressed their feeling of satisfaction of greater part of physiological need of Maslow’s hierarchy, having agreed that food and water are not a problem and with the hope that housing is a possibility. However, the non-satisfaction of the teachers in the area of conditions of service and payment of rent (shelters) which are captured by Oru (2006) on part of the physiological needs; it can be asserted that this level of Maslow’s hierarchy is yet to be satisfied by the teachers.

The finding that the teachers can cope with their pay but are not comfortable with their condition of service seems to be in agreement with Abd-el-Fattah (2010) who reported that pay increase does not have significant effect on the teacher’s job

satisfaction. This suggests that teachers seem to attach greater premium on other work conditions than the magnitude of their salaries which was the main focus of Abl-el-Fattah's study. There may be no doubt that job satisfaction can be enhanced more through good condition of service than magnitude of emolument.

From Table 2, majority of the teachers expressed satisfaction with item 1, that is, their job is not threatened by government policies. Conducive government policy as perceived by the teachers may have served as a favourable launching pad for the teachers. In the other items, majority of the teachers disagreed that their job is threatened by their boss and agreed that pursuit of further studies is not a threat to their job. They also disagreed that there is no fair treatment to all staff in their establishment, that is, there is no partiality in the treatment of staff in their schools. Majority of the teachers equally agreed that they have no fear for safety in the classroom and school environment as well as fear over protection against dismissal or undue transfer by their employer. However, majority of teachers express dissatisfaction with the provision of health care service by their establishment with the mean response of 2.10.

From the foregoing, the teachers seem to express satisfaction with majority of the items surveyed under level 2 of Maslow's hierarchy (safety needs). The response to the various items under the safety needs seem to agree with Ikenyiri and Ihua (2011) who reported that all levels of Maslow's need hierarchy were identified as satisfiers. This is because, all the items under this level of needs were also captured in Ikenyiri and Ihua (2011) study. We observed from the results on level 1 and 2 of Maslow's hierarchy, a situation where level 1 is not completely satisfied and level 2 almost completely satisfied. This seems to agree with the criticism of George and Baron (2013) that there is lack of hierarchical structure of needs as postulated by Maslow.

From Table 3, majority of the teachers disagreed that they are not loved by their students and their parents, that is, they are loved by their students and this is in line with item 2 and 3 where majority of the teachers agreed that they are respected by members of the community and also their relationship with their colleagues is cordial. Majority of the teachers disagreed that they are appreciated by the school authorities. This may not be unconnected with the type of interpersonal relationship with the authorities. Majority of the teachers also agreed that they are not allowed to participate actively in the formation of school club.

From the responses to the 6 items in table 3, we can see that there is agreement among the teachers, that is, there is more favourable relationship among their colleagues and students and their parents more than there is between them and the school authority. This is an indication that level 3 of Maslow's need hierarchy that is, social needs are partly satisfied and partly not satisfied based on the perception of the teachers under the items surveyed. Since some aspects of this level of needs are not satisfied, we can assert that this level of needs is not fully satisfied, because according to Ikenyiri and Ihua (2011), there is no level of Maslow's hierarchy that is not a satisfier of teacher's needs.

The test of hypothesis in Table 4 which showed that the responses of secondary school teachers on their satisfaction of Maslow's needs hierarchy is significantly

dependent on their qualifications is an indication that satisfaction of the various levels of Maslow's hierarchy by the teachers has something to do with the academic qualifications of the teachers. In other words, teachers with different qualifications perceive their satisfaction of Maslow's needs hierarchy differently. This may not be surprising. Qualification enhances socio-economic status of teachers in terms of placement, responsibility and salary, thus a teacher with first degree is placed higher than his NCE counterpart. With this higher rating the way a teacher with degree perceives the satisfaction of the needs hierarchy will certainly be different from that of an NCE teacher.

The test of hypothesis on Table 5 showed that gender has something to do with the way teachers perceive their satisfaction of Maslow's needs hierarchy. We can infer therefore that the satisfaction of Maslow's levels of human needs is biased in favour or against either man or woman. This may not be unconnected with the fact that in many of the schools, more male teachers have higher qualification and higher rating than women which in turn affect their perception. In addition, the varying degrees of role expectations and responsibilities placed on the male and female teachers can create differences in the way they perceive the satisfaction of Maslow's hierarchy of needs. This finding dismisses the fear of Mittelman (2013) who asserted that the small population of women used by Maslow in his study might have influenced the population validity of his findings.

In a similar vein, the test of hypothesis on Table 6 showed that the satisfaction of Maslow's levels of needs by the teachers has something to do their location. This means that the way a rural teacher perceives his satisfaction of Maslow's levels of needs is different from that of an urban teacher. Obviously, their social conditions and outlook are different and this can affect their perception. What may be enough for a rural teacher may just be a peanut for an urban teacher.

6. Conclusion

Since 1954 when Abraham Maslow came up with his theory on human needs, many of his critics have questioned the empirical and cultural validity of his findings. This work has lent support to the fact that the various levels of Maslow's needs hierarchy can be subjected to empiricism, yielding hard data that can be used to effect organizational growth.

It is hoped that with the findings and recommendations as presented, the relevant government agencies will address the gaps towards ensuring well motivated teachers in Kogi East Senatorial District. This, in turn, will translate into improved teaching and learning and performance of the students.

7. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made on the basis of the findings of the study:

- Government should not pay deaf ear to teachers' motivational needs especially in such areas like prompt payment of salaries and allowances.
- Government should provide good working condition. Teachers' welfare should be taken into consideration by the government.
- Promotion should be promptly effected and arrears paid in block or in reasonable installment to make teachers happy and instill in them more enthusiasm to perform their duties.
- Teachers should be part of decision making in their schools.
- Teachers' pension and gratuity should be paid promptly on retirement to remove anxiety from those approaching retirement.
- Teachers should be sponsored by government to workshops / conferences / seminars on regular basis to update their knowledge.
- School management should endeavour to create conducive atmosphere for cordial relationship between them and the teachers.
- Health services should be provided to schools to attend the needs of teacher and their families.

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